

Interview with a migrant in situation of vulnerability

Topic: Vulnerabilities Under the Global Protection Regime <https://www.vulner.eu/>

Place: Italy

Date: 2021-09-30

Language: English

I just want to ask you if you want to introduce yourself. Saying, for instance, your name or whatever... Pseudonym or a fantasy name, age and nationality.

Ok. I'm from Nigeria. My age is 25 years.

Ok. Where do you come from in Nigeria?

From Edo State.

From which family do you come from? What did your parents do in Nigeria? Or your sisters and brothers.

I come from a family of 6. 5 girls and 1 boy. I'm the first child of my parents. My siblings they are working. Some are (1:11), some do nails. (1:21 the other one do ... You know, what they call ...?).

Ok, I understand. And they all live in Nigeria?

Yes.

Ok. Do you have children? Are you married?

No, I'm not married, and I don't have children.

When did you arrive in Italy?

2015.

Ok. Did you immediately ask asylum?

No.

Ok. Did you stay in Roma all the time or did you move?

No, I came to Roma because I was arrested. I was staying in Sicily before.

Ok. You lived in Sicily for how much time?

I lived in Sicily almost... Because I have been in Roma almost 3 years now. So, I lived in Sicily for 3 years too.

Where in Sicily, do you remember?

Catania.

Ok. How did you arrive in Roma?

I arrived in Roma because I was arrested.

Arrested in Sicily?

No, in Roma.

You were travelling in Roma?

Yes. From Sicily to my boyfriend's house. I entered the Intercity Notte without the documents. Senza documento.

Did they bring you in Ponte Galeria?

Yes.

And then you arrived here.

Yes.

Did you ask asylum in Ponte Galeria?

Yes, because my lawyer told me to ask for asylum.

Ok. How was your asylum procedure? Is it finished? Do you have the document?

No. The first time I went to the Commission I had negative, so I'm waiting for an appeal, February 18. I'm now waiting for the result.

Ok. You went to the tribunal.

Yes

How was the first Commission? Did you feel good and comfortable to talk to them or not so much?

No, I was not feeling comfortable because most of them were Nigerians like me, the people that were there, the interpreter... They were from Nigeria, so I was not feeling comfortable.

Were you in the room with other Nigerians?

Yes.

Members of Commission?

Yes, members of Commission. There were a lot of Nigerian ladies there (4:05 interpreters) of Commission.

And you didn't like it.

No.

Were you in Ponte Galeria when you went to the Commission?

No, I was here. I stayed in Ponte Galeria for 5 days.

Fortunately.

Yes, because I didn't do anything, just because of the documents.

Of course. First Commission was not good. Instead, when you went to Tribunal, was it better?

No, I didn't go. My lawyer went for me.

Ok.

Yes, because the judge said she didn't want to see my presence. The lawyer did not even go, he said they talked through a video call on the laptop because of Coronavirus.

I understand. Did someone help you prepare the Commission and tell your story?

Yes.

Here in campo or other people also?

Here in camp, some other people, some organization, and the other lady that was working. She left the camp... I forgot her name, she worked here too.

Ok, another girl that...

Yes, she took care of the hospital and...

Also some other organizations outside of here or not?

I went to (5:38).

Ok. With the lawyer you feel good? With this person it was better the Commission, the meeting with the judge, the Tribunal?

I'm still waiting for the answer, because the lawyer said the judge has not given any answer yet. It's taking time.

Ok. In the past when you took contact with police or other offices, were they bad or were they good?

When I was arrested? It was good, they didn't do me anything because I didn't do anything apart from the documents. So it was good, they allowed me to use my phone, they bought me whatever I wanted. They were good to me.

Are you working now here in Marino?

No, I'm not working but I went to school of cooking, aiuto cuoca. We just finished last month (6:50).

Sorry, I don't remember. How many years are you here in camp?

3 years. End of August making it 3 years in camp.

Here always.

Yes.

Ok, so you are doing courses to work.

Yes. The first course I went to study for economica domestica. I finished that one, then last year I started the aiuto cuoca. We do it online because of Coronavirus. So I finished 2 months ago.

The place where you live now you like it?

Yes. A lot of my friends complain about their camp. Their camp is not good. But this place is perfect. It's ok because (7:49), you can go out whenever you want and you can come back. You can eat any kind of food you want to eat. They don't disturb you (8:00) African food. If you don't want to eat the other, you can eat African food, you can cook your food. There is no complaining. Just obey the rules and regulation.

Do you also like the people that work here?

Yes.

Do you feel supported? Do you feel good?

Yes I feel good. Just that the new ones I have not associated with them. So, it's just the old ones that was working here, that's the only people I normally talk with because Caterina (8:33) inside my room, it's only when I want to sign or when I have problems or maybe I'm sick and I ask for medicine. I'm always inside the room. So I feel good, because both of us, we haven't had problems. I haven't had any problems with the workers. I feel good. It's just that I don't associate with them, we are not friends, apart from Caterina, because Caterina understands me. But the rest... I don't associate with them.

With the other persons in camp do you feel good? Or do you have problems with some people?

No, I don't have problems with anybody. I feel good with everybody in the camp. It's just that I don't like to associate with people. I just like to be walking alone. We do play sometimes, when I'm in the mood to play. But when I'm not in the mood I'm always inside my room.

Ok. The relationship with other local services like hospitals or other offices, do you feel good there or there were some problems?

There have never been any problems. Whenever Milenia heard that I'm sick, even if she's not around, I would just send her a message and she would tell me "I'll look at what you take". But the recent one I'm not associated with her (10:26). So whenever I'm sick or I need any medicine, if Caterina is not around, I'll go to the pharmacy and buy it, just to avoid any problem.

Ok. If you want to reply something, how was your trip to arrive in Italy? Was it long, was it difficult, was it hard?

No, it was not difficult, it was just 3 weeks from Nigeria to this place.

How long sorry?

3 weeks.

Was it by car always and boat?

Yes, by car and boat.

Did some person helped you organize the trip?

Yes, of course.

The experience during the trip was...

It was ok.

Was it bad, was it good?

No, it was not bad. For me it was not bad but a lot of people say their trip was bad, some stayed on the road for one year, some stayed for three months, but mine was not long.

It was not so bad. Ok. Here in Italy, especially the first period, was it good for you or something happened that you don't like?

No. In Italy the first period... It was not so good, because... You know, we Nigerians...

Yeah, I know...

Yes, so we (12:04) somebody that brought us to come and be in prostitution, they lie to you...

Yes, I know...

...You want to come, but when you get here, they will ask you to go and do prostitution. So that was just...

It was bad.

Yes, it was really bad.

But you did escape from this situation.

No, I didn't escape because I didn't have anybody in Italy. I don't know any citizen. I was still (12:35), I was 19 years old. I don't have friends, I don't have anybody. So I didn't escape.

Did you have a boyfriend here in Roma when you moved here or you just visit friends? When they stopped you in train.

Yes, then I had a boyfriend here, because I wasn't having any connection with the people that brought me here. I finished paying them, so I can do whatever I want to do. I can go anywhere I want to go.

Ok. Thank you. It was very... Thank you. Do you think that you suffered some form of discrimination here? Do you feel that people here discriminate you for racial reasons? Or you feel good?

Yes, Italy is one of the most peaceful places I have ever seen. Although I have not travelled due to sometimes I watch news, most of my friends outside their countries, (13:57 France) they are planning to come back to Italy. I feel good in Italy. Even without documents you can work freely, just don't have problems with anybody and you can do whatever you want to do. I feel good and I don't think I'm living Italy to another country. I'm just praying to have documents and a good job. [crosstalk] apart from my relationship status, nobody is giving me problems.

If you have some problems do you have some supportive person around you, here in campo, or I don't know, other associations.

Yes. I have not been in any other association apart during the time of my Commission. They sent me to an association. If I have any problem, if I don't know how to deal with it myself I would go to Caterina because Caterina is the only person that understands. We have a bond together, so she understands me a lot and I understand her a lot. If Caterina is not around, maybe she went to (15:09) I cannot go inside the office and talk to another person because I don't trust them. So it's only Caterina ever since I have been in this camp, for 3 years, she has always been here. So if I have any problem, she has been the only...

Very supportive.

Yes.

Which are your most urgent needs today or desires for the future?

I just need (15:41). It's the only thing that is bothering me is the document. So after this document... But for now I'm searching for a job because they said you can't work without the documents, because I have (15:53) and I can't use carta d'identità to work. I can't use it (15:58) without the certificate of the school I went to, so I can't work. So the main things I need is the document.

In the end, on the basis of your experience, what do you think could be improved in the Italian system that you don't like? For example the Commission, you told you didn't like the Commission. Or maybe too much time...

No, not too much time. Why I don't like the Commission in the first place is because those people are always interviewing somebody, some are Nigerians, some are not Nigerians, but they speak English and they are black like me. So (16:57). So that is the situation. When you are like me, you can't force me to say what I don't want to say. So I only say it because I want to say it. If I say that I don't want to say this thing, you won't force me to say it. So it's like they were forcing me "if you say it, they are going to give you documents. If you say someone that brought you, they are going to give you documents". If you say this, if you say that... But you can't force me to say. If I say it's not somebody that brought me, take it like that. If you like it, give me documents. If you don't like it (17:27). They are trying to force me. That's why I was not good to speak in Commission. It was not even (17:38 3 months) they give me negative.

So they were very... They asked you many questions. I know that Commission is very....

And I was not prepared. Caterina was not around then. It was only one woman, so they didn't tell me "look at what you are going to say". The second one, if I went there, Caterina prepared everything. She read it out (18:06) she corrected it, so we made sure that everything was ok. But the first time she was not around, she went for (18:15), so the Nigerian that was here, she also... It's the same thing. So that's why I wasn't associating with her. I believe that's why they gave me negative the first time.

It's always so hard that people judge your story in any kind.

Yes, in any kind, especially with Nigerians. Instead of you to tell your past to (18:42) you have to tell it to Nigerians. (18:45) because most of us we do judge our friends or our partner with what they tell us. So you then are having some kind of issue, they will use that word against you, so it's better to just keep it to yourself than telling it to Nigerians.

Thank you. Do you think you want to add something that we don't see? I don't know, something advice or questions that we can tell to Italy's system or I don't know... About accoglienza, camps, about something.

All I just want to say is that, especially we Africans, we should try and be patient. I have been here for 3 years and I believe that (19:37) have the documents. We should not try and leave the camp, we should just try to be patient and obey the rules and regulations of the camp, because most of my friends they ran out of this place and they are in the streets. They don't have anywhere to stay, some are even looking for a way to come back to the camp, but there is no way. So every little opportunity you have, you just have to be patient. If they are asking you to go to school, go do that.

Anywhere they ask me to go (20:06). If they say “come and go to school” I will go. So they just have to be patient and I believe that the documents will come. It only takes time.

Ok, I really thank you. Thank you for telling me your experience, and also some part of your story that was very hard.